

DIRECTIONS FOR PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT OF THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the experience of developed countries in providing employment to the population, highlights the factors that cause unemployment. The employment and unemployment rate in the country, their changes and employment are analyzed by industry. Proposals have also been developed to provide employment and reduce unemployment.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has had and continues to have a major impact on employment. In addition to threats to public health, economic and social unrest threaten the long-term lives and well-being of millions of people. In addition to the fight against the disease, the task of ensuring the stability of the population's employment has become one of the urgent issues for the governments. This is especially true in countries where the spread of the disease has been strong, including the USA, European countries, Russia, China, South Korea, India, African countries, and other countries, and employment has become an actual trend.

The International Labor Organization (ILO) is working on about 700 active programs and projects in more than 100 countries of the world to help ensure the employment of the population. Also, ILO has been supporting the technical, organizational and institutional capabilities of countries to ensure the sustainable development of employment [19].

Among the countries where the global pandemic is receding, in 2020, the unemployment rate caused by the pandemic has decreased in Uzbekistan, and existing jobs are being restored. However, employment has not returned to pre-pandemic levels. The main reason for this is related to external migration.

According to the information of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, the number of labor migrants working in other countries in our country today is 2.6 million. is more than 7.5% of the total population and 13.6% of the total labor resources. Many labor migrants returned to our country due to the closure of many workplaces and difficult living conditions due to the pandemic. This led to an increase in the unemployment rate and a decrease in the income of the population.

Therefore, at the initiative of the head of our state, consistent measures aimed at creating new jobs by encouraging active entrepreneurship, improving the investment climate

and business environment are being implemented. In particular, the decision PQ-3856 [1] of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 14, 2018 "On measures to improve and increase the efficiency of work on ensuring the employment of the population" was adopted. Also, in the republic, effective measures are being taken to implement programs to ensure employment of the population, to improve employment mechanisms for vacant and quota jobs, and to develop effective forms of self-employment.

However, there is still a high level of tension in the labor market in the regions, the issues of establishing permanent jobs, ensuring employment of young people, women, and members of low-income families, especially in rural areas, as well as regulating the processes of external labor migration, are not being resolved. This shows how relevant the topic is and the need to carry out scientific research in this regard.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Ensuring the employment of the population has always been one of the urgent issues. Especially in the context of the global pandemic, it has once again shown that the issue of employment is one of the global problems and requires more scientific research in this regard. Including:

From foreign scientists, B.D. Breev[2], V.N. on informal employment and its impact on public finances. Salin and V.V. Narbutis[3], E.A. on statistical analysis of employment and unemployment. Dolgikh[4], C. Krittanawong, A. Kumar, Z. Wang, U. Baber, and DL Bhatt [5], Effects of Demographic Changes on Population Employment on Self-Employment and Long-Working Cardiovascular Disease Risk by P.Ge, W.Sun and Z.Zhao [6] and J. Grashuis on Continuity and Competitiveness Analysis of Self-Employment in the Time of the COVID-19 Pandemic[7] are conducting scientific research.

Local scientists D.A. Nasimov [8] improved the methodological and methodological foundations of the introduction of modern forms of employment in the conditions of the digital economy, M.K. Abdullaev and D.B. Begalovlar [9] analyzed employment indicators in our country, S.A. Bozorova [10] the state of the service sector in increasing the employment of the population, A.B. Irmatova [11] discussed the problems of engaging women in intellectual work, A. Tashpulatov [12] and Sh.R. Kholmuminov, B.Kh. Umurzakov, T.A. Makhmudov [13] has been researching the strategic socio-economic importance of reducing the employment of rural residents and their informal employment.

In addition to the results of these studies, their scientifically based proposals, practical recommendations and conclusions, it is worth saying that solving the existing problems of providing employment to the population and carrying out statistical analyzes on this, further scientific research of the organizational, economic and institutional aspects of solving the problem, it is also necessary to develop innovative approaches.

Research methodology

In this research, expert assessment, comparison, comparative analysis and systematic approach methods, statistical tables and graphs and diagrams, as well as official statistical data from the International Labor Organization, the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, and the scientific research of local and foreign scientists related to the research topic. research works were widely used.

Analysis and results

Due to the integration of countries' economies and the development of interstate socio-economic, strategic relations, as well as countries with stagnant or low population growth due to low birth rates (European countries, Russia, South Korea, etc.), international labor migration is increasingly expanding.

This process benefits every country. That is, if migrant workers contribute to the growth and development of the destination countries, they will bring great benefits to their countries through remittances and the experience they acquire.

However, management of the migration process, protection of migrant workers, migration and development relations, and international cooperation issues are among the complex issues to regulate.

In countries with high population growth and most developing and underdeveloped countries, there are sufficient problems in providing employment to the population. For example, the lack of jobs, low monthly salaries, lack of professional qualifications and knowledge of labor resources are among them.

There are five main causes of unemployment in the economy [14]:

- related to the introduction of new technologies and other structural changes in the economy;
- economic recession leading to a decrease in demand for labor resources;
- government policy, an increase in the minimum wage, and therefore a decrease in the demand for labor;
- seasonal fluctuations in some sectors of the economy;
- demographic changes, that is, the growth of the working age population.

Developed countries have created their own models for eliminating unemployment and ensuring employment of the population and have been using them in the policy of ensuring employment of the population.

In the conditions of the most developed market economy, the following models of employment policy are used [15]:

1. **European model**- implies a decrease in the number of workers and an increase in the income of workers with an increase in labor productivity.
2. **Scandinavian model**- based on providing employment to almost all those in need by creating jobs in the public sector at an average wage level.
3. **American model**- based on the creation of jobs that do not require high productivity for a large part of the economically active population. Unemployment will decrease, but the number of low-income residents will increase.

Today, practical measures are being implemented in our country to ensure the employment of the population. In particular, it includes all-round support of entrepreneurship and small business, family entrepreneurship and self-employment, as well as increasing the employment of the population based on the creation of new jobs by creating favorable conditions for their development.

As of January 2021, the population of our country is 34.6 million. 17.5 mln. in cities and 17.1 mln. some of them live in rural areas.

The population density in the republic is 77 thousand people per 1 sq.km. However, the population distribution by regions differs sharply, in particular, in the Republic of

Karakalpakstan there are 11.5 thousand people per 1 sq. km, in Andijan 741.4 thousand, in Bukhara 48.4 thousand, in Jizzakh 66.5 thousand, in Kashkadarya 116.7 thousand, 9.1 thousand in Navoi, 385.4 thousand in Namangan, 235.4 thousand in Samarkand, 133.4 thousand in Surkhandarya, 201.2 thousand in Syrdarya, 196.3 thousand in Tashkent, 565.1 thousand in Fergana, 312.9 thousand in Khorezm and Tashkent city and it is 7874.1 thousand people. This indicates the strength of internal labor migration in regions with different levels of socio-economic development.

According to the analysis, the number of labor resources in the republic is 19.1 million. making up 55.9% of the permanent population. 19.01 million of total labor resources. people or 99.5 percent of them are working-age population, 0.09 million of them. or 0.5 percent are workers younger than and older than the working age (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of composition of labor resources in Uzbekistan (thousands of people)

Composition of labor resources	2000	2004	2008	2012	2016	2020
Labor resources	12469.0	14048.8	15685.7	17564.3	18488.9	19142.3
<i>relative to the permanent population, in percent</i>	50.6	54.3	57.5	59.0	58.1	55.9
including:						
Working population of working age	12245.4	13880.4	15474.6	17451.5	18371.7	19052.0
<i>relative to the permanent population, in percent</i>	49.7	53.7	56.7	58.6	57.7	55.7
<i>in relation to labor resources, in percent</i>	98.2	98.8	98.7	99.4	99.4	99.5
Workers under and over the working age	223.6	168.4	211.1	112.8	117.2	95.1
<i>relative to the permanent population, in percent</i>	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.4	0.4	0.3
<i>in relation to labor resources, in percent</i>	1.8	1.2	1.3	0.6	0.6	0.5

Source:Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Total labor resources77.3 percent or 14.8 million. one is an economically active population. Also 13.2 mln. 69.2 percent of people or labor resources are employed in the economy (Table 1).

Table 1

Labor resources and population employment by regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan (thousands of people)

No	The name of the areas	Labor resources	Economically active population	Jobs in the economy
1	Republic of	1069.0	781.7	699.3

	Karakalpakstan			
2	Andijan	1752.9	1387.3	1236.7
3	Bukhara	1070.4	876.7	783.6
4	Jizzakh	774.6	598.9	533.1
5	Kashkadarya	1817.6	1334.2	1186.7
6	Navoi	556.3	446.2	404.3
7	Namangan	1579.5	1205.3	1078.0
8	Samarkand	2130.4	1585.4	1410.9
9	Surkhandarya	1457.6	1104.1	982.0
10	Syr Darya	485.7	375.1	333.7
11	Tashkent	1614.9	1336.5	1195.6
12	Ferghana	2068.5	1613.9	1438.3
13	Khorezm	1042.4	800.8	713.7
14	Tashkent city	1722.3	1351.8	1243.7
Total by Republic:		19142.3	14797.9	13239.6

Source: Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to the analysis, 3.6 million of the employed population in 2020. people or 26.9 percent are engaged in agriculture, forestry and fisheries, 1.8 million. people or 13.5 percent of the industry, 1.3 mln. people or 9.6 percent construction, 1.4 mln. people or 10.3 percent trade, 0.6 mln. people or 4.7 percent of transportation and storage, 1.1 mln. people or 8.8 percent of education, 0.7 mln. people or 4.9 percent of health and social services and 2.7 mln. or 21.3 percent are contributed by other types of activities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Composition of the employed population by types of economic activity (thousands of people).

Source: Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The analysis shows that in 2020, the level of employment increased by 113.9% compared to 2010 and 101.4% compared to 2015, according to the types of economic activity, agriculture, forestry and fishing increased by 114.2 and 98.8%, industry by 111.5 and 101.2 percent, construction 122.6 and 103.7 percent, trade 110.4 and 96.5 percent, transportation and storage 122.2 and 101.4 percent, education 105.3 and 104.9 percent, health and social

services increased by 109.4 and 108.4 percent, and other types of activity increased by 116.3 and 103.4 percent.

Also, the employed population according to the results of the analysis of the types of ownership, the number of jobs in the public sector in 2020 is 2.5 million. and 10.7 million jobs in the non-state sector. established a person. In recent years, the number of people employed in public sectors has been increasing. In particular, the growth rate of banking in the public sector was 98.0 percent in 2012 (compared to 2010), 98.4 percent in 2014 (compared to 2012), 100.2 percent in 2016 (compared to 2014), 2018 (compared to 2016) 104.1 percent, increased to 102.9 percent in 2020 (compared to 2018) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of the employed population by types of ownership (thousands of people).

Source: Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

As of January 2021 [18], the number of unemployed people registered by labor offices in our country was 37,100. This indicator has increased almost 2.3 times compared to 2010, its growth rate was 0.4% in 2000, 0.4% in 2004, 4.9% in 2008, 4.9% in 2012, 5.2% in 2016. and in 2020 it was 110.5 percent (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The growth rate of employment and unemployment levels (the number of the employed population in relation to the number of the working-age population, in percent).

Source: Information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In our country, the employment rate of the employed population compared to the population of working age was 67.7% on average during the years 2000-2020. In particular, it was 69.4 percent in 2000, 67.7 percent in 2004, 67.6 percent in 2008, 66.6 percent in 2012, 68.7 percent in 2016, and 66.1 percent in 2020.

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the above, it is appropriate to take into account the following in order to ensure the employment of the population in our country and reduce the level of unemployment:

1. It is necessary to deeply analyze the problems of increasing employment of the population from the bottom to the top and develop practical solutions and control their implementation.
2. Usually the shadow economy plays an important role in reducing unemployment. Therefore, in the fight against the hidden economy, it is necessary to organize not by bureaucratic means, but by applying economic incentives.
3. In parallel with the demographic changes of the population, it is necessary to increase new jobs and use the experiences of developed countries in this regard.
4. As a result of the digitalization of the economy, the resulting unemployment rate will be higher than the new occupations that will emerge. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the number of unskilled jobs in the state and non-state sectors, and in particular, self-employment should be further encouraged.
5. Today's database of vacancies is among non-governmental sectors based on a number of online platforms. However, there is very little information about job vacancies on public sector websites, and most recruitment processes are closed and narrow. This has a negative impact not only on employment, but also on the productivity of these agencies. Therefore, it is necessary to create a single online platform of complete information about vacancies in the public and private sectors.
6. It is necessary to expand the activities of state and non-state agencies for people who need social protection and have difficulty finding work, and strengthen control over them.

In conclusion, it should be noted that first of all, it is necessary to carry out a real and correct polling of the population. It serves to increase the effectiveness of the results of analysis and research on the demographic change of the population and ensuring employment. It also allows for realistic development of promising strategies to ensure employment of the population, reduce unemployment and improve living conditions. In general, the use of appropriate wage rates for the creation of new jobs not only has a positive effect on labor productivity, but also leads to an increase in the level of socio-economic development.

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